

IMPROVING FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION ACTIVITY IN SOLVING CRIMES: ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE FORENSIC BIOLOGY DEPARTMENT

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The role of forensic medical examination bodies in the timely and complete detection of crimes is invaluable. Especially in crimes such as murder, infliction of bodily harm, theft, rape, and sexual assault, the identification of biological evidence is of great importance. Therefore, improving the efficiency of forensic medical experts and enhancing laboratory activities is one of the urgent tasks.

Expert examinations are carried out in accordance with the requirements of the Criminal Procedure Code (CPC) of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to Article 203 of the CPC, circumstances such as the origin, reliability, ownership, and intended use of material evidence must be comprehensively examined.

Material evidence of a biological nature is submitted to the laboratory based on a decision to appoint a forensic medical examination.

Analysis of the Activities of the Forensic Biology Department

The activities of the forensic biology department play an important role in solving crimes in the Surkhandarya region. The department staff identify, preserve, and analyze material evidence using modern laboratory methods.

The following are examined as biological material evidence: blood, hair, saliva, semen, sweat, skin fragments, and other biomaterials. Their physicochemical properties and biological origin are determined using advanced laboratory techniques.

According to the results of expert examinations, it was established that in 2019 – 17, in 2020 – 23, and in 2021 – 14 minor girls became victims of sexual assault. This indicates the high social danger of such crimes and further increases the importance of forensic biological examinations.

Out of 54 examinations conducted in the department, 9 were completed within 1–10 days, 13 within 11–20 days, and 32 within 21–30 days.

In addition, all 54 examinations conducted based on forensic medical referrals were completed within the prescribed time limits.

According to the analysis results, laboratory activities generally ensure that examinations are completed within the established deadlines. However, in some cases,

the extension of examination periods up to 21–30 days may be due to the large workload and limited technical resources.

Actions aimed at concealing or destroying traces of crimes are also being uncovered through laboratory analyses. This demonstrates the strategic importance of the forensic biology department in criminalistics.

Forensic medical examination, especially the activities of the forensic biology department, plays a decisive role in solving crimes. Scientific analysis of biological material evidence contributes to a complete and fair investigation of crimes. Statistical data show that expert examinations are being carried out systematically.

At the same time, the efficiency of this field can be further improved through the wide introduction of modern technologies and the enhancement of organizational measures.

References

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